

Dynamic Channel Encryption Using Fluid Antennas for Secure and Private Communication

Javier Otero Martinez, Kun Chen-Hu, and Ana García Armada

Department of Signal Theory and Communications, Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain

E-mails: {jotero, kchen, agarcia}@tsc.uc3m.es

Abstract—Future 6G communication systems will require the integration of innovative technologies capable of supporting a wide range of advanced services, while simultaneously ensuring stronger security and privacy guarantees for end users. Fluid antenna (FA) systems are reconfigurable devices that have emerged as a promising solution due to their adaptability to dynamic environments and rapidly changing network demands. In this work, we investigate the use of liquid-based FA to enhance physical-layer security by exploiting their reconfigurability, enabling a novel precoding and combining mechanism. This mechanism is intrinsically tied to the physical configuration of the FA and is capable of safeguarding the integrity of transmitted symbols, effectively mitigating the risks of both eavesdropping when compared to existing techniques. Additionally, we show that it protects against fake data injection by interpreting such data as incorrect, using theoretical and numerical methodologies. Overall, we introduce a new use case for FA as a physical-layer defense tool, laying the groundwork for their adoption in secure and resilient 6G wireless networks.

Index Terms—Fluid Antenna, Reconfigurable Antenna, Spatial Correlation, Physical Layer Security

I. INTRODUCTION

Current communication systems face significant challenges on the path to next-generation networks. The rising demand for higher bandwidth, lower latency, and massive device connectivity calls for more efficient and scalable infrastructure [1]. Meeting these demands requires not only advancing our current technologies but also developing novel and innovative solutions. However, these improvements must be accompanied by enhanced physical layer security (PLS) [2]. Adversaries may attempt to eavesdrop on transmissions or inject malicious data to deceive legitimate users, posing a serious threat to the integrity and reliability of communication networks.

Systems based on fluid antennas (FA) [3] are an emerging type of communication technology that explores high reconfigurability by taking advantage of their ability to reversibly change their shape. Unlike traditional solid-state antennas with fixed structures, they unlock an additional degree of freedom for designing communication technologies and use cases. Moreover, liquid antennas are a subset of FA that utilize liquid materials as main conductors.

Some existing studies have explored FA for various applications, such as user access [4], integrated sensing and communications (ISAC) [5], and even defensive strategies [6]. They consistently demonstrated that the reconfigurability of FA can enhance security and privacy by leveraging spatial diversity. In [7], a closed-form expression for FA performance

in correlated Nakagami- m environments is derived, with particular emphasis on improving PLS.

Unfortunately, some optimization-based methods require extensive computational resources and prolonged processing times, which could even make them impractical for real-time applications due to latency constraints [8], motivating further research. Moreover, the (partial) knowledge of channel state information (CSI) of the adversary is typically considered, which is difficult to justify in realistic scenarios [9]. Additionally, these techniques often rely on side links to share information between network nodes, such as antenna position updates. Thus, additional communication overheads and synchronization challenges are introduced as well.

One specific approach to prevent eavesdropping involves combining FA with artificial noise (AN) [10], which introduces randomness into the transmitted symbols. As adversaries lack knowledge of the noise sequence, it becomes significantly more difficult to extract data or pilot signals. However, this method comes at the cost of reduced signal to noise ratio (SNR), since part of the transmit power is diverted to noise rather than the useful signal. As a result, communication performance degrades, and frequent CSI updates are required, increasing system overhead.

Given the limitations of previous techniques, we propose a novel defensive method that exploits the features of fluid antennas [11]. It is based on encryption and decryption of the transmitted symbols through the design of precoding and combining matrices, respectively. By purposefully altering the data symbols to be transmitted via FA, eavesdropping can be effectively prevented. Only the FA at the legitimate receiver can reverse the effect of the precoder and recover the original transmitted symbols. If an attacker injects malicious data symbols, the legitimate receiver would make an erroneous detection, as the combining process would distort the injected data symbols. Since gains of both the precoding and combining matrices are normalized to unity, the proposed approach does not degrade the SNR, making it more efficient when compared to AN techniques. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, this is the first time a fluid antenna has been proposed as a defense mechanism against fake data injection, which served as the main motivation of our work.

A performance assessment based on numerical evaluation is obtained in terms of achievable secrecy rate (ASR) and the probability of detecting injected false symbols. The results not only verify the theoretical analysis but also highlight that the

Fig. 1. Illustrative example of eavesdropping and fake data injection in downlink.

proposed architecture significantly outperforms the existing technique in the literature, making it a reliable system to be used in future wireless networks.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the system model for the cellular network with the presence of attackers and describes the particular FA architecture. Section III details the novel concept and design of the novel encryption and decryption matrices to avoid eavesdropping and fake data injection. Several numerical results are provided in Section IV to evaluate the performance of the proposed system. Section V concludes the paper with a summary of findings and insights.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

The considered scenario is built by a legitimate communication link between a base station (BS) and user equipment (UE). In addition to that, one adversarial BS (A-BS) is also present. The latter is not only eavesdropping on the legitimate communication link, but it would also be injecting fake data symbols. Hence, the A-BS is disrupting the privacy and security of an existing communication system. In the present work, it is considered that all terminals are equipped with a liquid antenna, which behaves as a single-element antenna.

The chosen waveform corresponds to the well-known orthogonal frequency division multiplexing (OFDM), which is deployed in the current 5G [12]. It is assumed that a slot is built by K subcarriers and N consecutive OFDM symbols. A time-division duplexing (TDD) scheme is adopted, where the downlink and uplink transmissions are allocated in different OFDM symbols within one slot. It is considered that the coherence time of all channels is long enough to cope within, at least, one slot. In addition, the cyclic prefix (CP) is long enough to absorb the multi-path effects of all channels, avoiding the inter-carrier interference (ICI) and inter-symbol interference (ISI) in the OFDM signal. Consequently, without loss of generality and for the sake of the space, a particular subcarrier of the OFDM symbol, out of K , is taken into consideration.

A. Eavesdropping and Fake Data Injection

At the receiver, after discarding the CP and performing the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), the eavesdropped signal of the A-BS at the n -th OFDM symbol and the subcarrier of interest can be modeled as

$$y_{a,b,n} = h_{a,b,n}x_{b,n} + w_{a,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{DL}}, \quad (1)$$

$$y_{a,u,n} = h_{a,u,n}x_{u,n} + w_{a,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{UL}}, \quad (2)$$

respectively, where $x_{b,n}$ and $x_{u,n}$ are the transmitted data symbols from the BS and UE at the n -th OFDM symbol and the subcarrier of interest, respectively. $w_{a,n}$ accounts for the additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN) of the A-BS at the n -th OFDM symbol and the subcarrier of interest. It is modeled as a circularly symmetric, zero-mean complex Gaussian random variable with distribution $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{w_a}^2)$. \mathcal{N}^{DL} and \mathcal{N}^{UL} are the two subsets that contain the OFDM symbol indices for the downlink and uplink transmissions within one slot, respectively. $h_{a,b,n}$ and $h_{a,u,n}$ are the channel frequency response coefficients between the A-BS \leftrightarrow BS and A-BS \leftrightarrow UE, respectively, at the n -th OFDM symbol at the subcarrier of interest.

Meanwhile, the received signal of the legitimate UE and BS at the n -th OFDM symbol and the subcarrier of interest can be modeled as

$$y_{u,n} = h_{b,u,n}x_{b,n} + h_{a,u,n}x_{a,n} + w_{u,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{DL}}, \quad (3)$$

$$y_{b,n} = h_{b,u,n}x_{u,n} + h_{a,b,n}x_{a,n} + w_{b,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{UL}}, \quad (4)$$

where $w_{u,n}$ and $w_{b,n}$ account for the AWGN of the UE and BS at the n -th OFDM symbol and the subcarrier of interest, whose distributions follow $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{w_u}^2)$ and $\mathcal{CN}(0, \sigma_{w_b}^2)$, respectively. $h_{b,u,n}$ is the channel frequency response between the BS \leftrightarrow UE at the n -th OFDM symbol at the subcarrier of interest.

B. Fluid Antenna

We consider a device acting as a single antenna element and employing a single radio-frequency (RF) chain. This device consists of a tube that serves as a container for a drop of eGain. This drop acts as a radiating element, which can move inside the tube with speed v_c [m/s] to reach a set of defined configurations often referred to as “ports”. The position of the drop can be computed simply as

$$r[m] = r[0] \pm v_c m, \quad (5)$$

where $r[m]$ is an arbitrary position measured in millimeters, $r[0]$ is the initial position, and m is the temporal sample. Moving the drop could be achieved by applying a direct current excitation only, thanks to a phenomenon called Continuous Electrowetting (CEW) [13]. It is crucial to consider a simple reconfiguration mechanism that would allow the development of feasible use cases. Therefore, CEW requires small DC excitations that are compatible with RF signals used for communications. Our preliminary tests ensure that drop

Fig. 2. Sketch of a FA

speeds of the order of ~ 50 mm/s can be achieved when applying signals of the order of 1 V.

The tube has a fixed length of $W\lambda$, expressed in wavelengths of the signal to be used for communications. Therefore, the physical dimensions of the device are expected to be on the order of a few centimeters, for communications under 6 GHz. An illustrative scheme of the FA model can be seen in Fig. 2. As a consequence, the proposed eGaIn antenna would be able to capture incoming signals that have experienced different propagation channels depending on the position of the drop. The position of the drop is always known, and it is assumed to accelerate instantaneously.

In consequence, if a narrowband signal is transmitted, channel coefficients, h , have the form

$$h_{\text{DL}} = h_{b,u,n} \exp(j\theta_{b,n}), \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{DL}}, \quad (6)$$

$$h_{\text{UL}} = h_{b,u,n} \exp(j\theta_{u,n}), \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{UL}}, \quad (7)$$

where $\theta_{b,n}$ and $\theta_{u,n}$ are two variable phases at the BS and UE, respectively, which are dynamically modifying the resulting CSI. These phase rotations are caused by the different experienced delays τ_n as $e^{-j2\pi f_c \tau_n}$. Note that even though the channel is considered to be static, different τ_n are expected because of the changes in the topology of the FA, which is varying in space. For our application, these particular changes in phase are explored to improve the security aspect of a communication system.

It is commonly assumed in the literature [3] that port positions are continuous, implying no “empty” space between them. As a result, high correlation values are expected when the associated distance between ports is less than $\lambda/2$ [14]. However, unlike conventional setups, the proposed use case does not require a specific channel response but instead relies on distinct enough channel coefficients at each port. Consequently, the received signal phase becomes a function of the propagation delay, which in turn depends on the port position, itself determined by the speed of the drop. This chain of dependencies introduces a phase rotation factor ($\theta_{b,n}$ and $\theta_{u,n}$) into the channel coefficients. By design, the phase

Fig. 3. Hypothetical reflectors to create artificial changes in received phase. They might be unevenly spaced along the container.

remains constant within an OFDM symbol duration; thus, reconfiguration occurs only between consecutive symbols.

III. DEFENSIVE FLUID ANTENNA AGAINST EAVESDROPPING AND FAKE DATA INJECTION

We are proposing a novel defensive system against eavesdropping and fake data injection based on the design of a pair of precoder and combiner using a FA. The legitimate entities can precode the transmit signals and combine the received ones by exploiting a fluid antenna thanks to its reconfigurability. This would represent a novel use case for FA technologies. Without loss of generality and for the sake of conciseness, the downlink case is detailed, meanwhile, the uplink case can be easily generalized.

This precoding mechanism is based on the reconfiguration capabilities of the FA, thanks to the previously mentioned phase rotation factor. In accordance with the literature [15], it can be assumed that the phase shift from one port to another is constant, analogously to multi-antenna devices. These shifts should change linearly with drop speed for our proposed topology. Consequently, the receiver perceives phase variations in steps of a particular size that is dependent on port spacing. Note that it will be limited by the physical dimensions of the device. For security applications, exhibiting a constant drop speed would not be convenient since the eavesdropper could learn from it eventually. Therefore, drop speed is assumed to change its direction with time to mitigate this effect. Furthermore, our proposed design only requires distinct incoming signals, which could be forced using reflectors or other external tools, as shown in Figure 3, to increase the performance of the precoding factor.

A. Precoding and Combining using a Fluid Antenna

When referring to the downlink, the complex symbols transmitted by the BS ($x_{b,n}$), which belong to a quadrature amplitude modulation (QAM) constellation, must be precoded by the fluid antenna (encryption). Later, the UE, before making the symbol decision, must make use of a combiner to undo the effect of the precoder (decryption).

Considering (2) and the time-varying response of the FA, the eavesdropped symbols at A-BS in the downlink ($y_{a,b,n}$) can be rewritten as

$$y_{a,b,n} = h_{a,b,n} \exp(j\theta_{b,n}) x_{b,n} + w_{a,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{DL}}. \quad (8)$$

The A-BS cannot successfully decode the transmitted symbols by the legitimate one ($x_{b,n}$), unless it is capable of finding out the chosen precoder by the FA ($\theta_{b,n}$).

Simultaneously, the A-BS can also inject fake data symbols, and according to (3), the received symbols at the UE in the downlink ($y_{u,n}$) can be written as

$$y_{u,n} = h_{b,u,n} \exp(j\theta_{b,n}) x_{b,n} + h_{a,b,n} x_{a,n} + w_{u,n}, \quad n \in \mathcal{N}^{\text{DL}} \quad (9)$$

Assuming the worst-case scenario, which corresponds to the received signal power from the A-BS being significantly higher than the legitimate BS at the UE, it will estimate the channel between the A-BS and UE and equalize the received symbols. The FA will firstly undo the effect of the precoder, and later, the received symbols will be equalized as

$$z_{u,n} = h_{a,b,n}^{-1} \exp(-j\theta_{b,n}) y_{u,n} = \exp(-j\theta_{b,n}) x_{a,n} + h_{a,b,n}^{-1} \exp(-j\theta_{b,n}) w'_{u,n}, \quad (10)$$

$$w'_{u,n} = h_{b,u,n} \exp(j\theta_{b,n}) x_{b,n} + w_{u,n}, \quad (11)$$

where $w'_{u,n}$ is the interference and noise term. It is showing that the UE will wrongly decode those symbols transmitted by the A-BS thanks to the use of a combiner ($\theta_{b,n}$) at the fluid antenna.

B. Eavesdropping: Analysis of the ASR

The ASR is analyzed for the eavesdropping stage. It accounts for the amount of information eavesdropped by A-BS as compared to the information received by the legitimate receiver. In this case, A-BS is only listening to the data information transmitted by both legitimate entities of the link (BS and UE). The achievable rate communication link between the BS and UE is obtained as

$$C_{b,u} = \log_2(1 + \rho_{b,u}), \quad (12)$$

$$\rho_{b,u} = \frac{\mathbb{E}\{|h_{b,u}|^2\}}{\sigma_w^2} = \frac{\sigma_{b,u}^2}{\sigma_w^2}, \quad \mathbb{E}\{|x_{b,n}|^2\} = 1, \quad (13)$$

where $\rho_{b,u}$ is the SNR of the legitimate link between BS and UE. Analogously to (12), we can compute $C_{a,b}$ and $\rho_{a,b}$.

Then, the ASR [16] between the legitimate and eavesdropping links measures the amount of information eavesdropped by A-BS as compared to the legitimate link, which can be defined as

$$E_{b,u} = \begin{cases} C_{b,u} - C_{a,b} & \rho_{b,u} > \rho_{a,b} \\ 0 & \rho_{b,u} \leq \rho_{a,b} \end{cases}, \quad (14)$$

To avoid A-BS accessing the information transmitted by the legitimate links, precoding is required to mask the transmitted information. However, the A-BS may try to hack the system

and get the chosen precoder, and hence, (14) can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} E_{b,u} &= \frac{N_r}{N} C_{b,u} + \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) (C_{b,u} - C_{a,u}) \\ &= C_{b,u} - \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) C_{a,u}, \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

where N_r is the amount of time measured in OFDM symbols that A-BS requires to find out the used precoder. On one hand, the first term of (15) accounts for the ASR of the link when A-BS has not discovered the used precoders yet, and hence, she is not able to obtain any information. On the other hand, the second term of (15) points out the ASR once A-BS has found out the precoders, and therefore, the term $C_{a,u}$ is penalizing the expression.

After performing some manipulations, (15) is simplified as

$$E_{b,u} = \log_2(1 + \rho_{b,u}) - \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) \log_2(1 + \rho_{a,u}) \quad (16)$$

If the SNR of legitimate and adversarial links are higher than unity, (16) can be approximated by

$$E_{b,u} \approx \log_2(\rho_{b,u}) - \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) \log_2(\rho_{a,u}). \quad (17)$$

Substituting (13) into (17), the ASR between the legitimate link and the link between BS \leftrightarrow A-BS and UE \leftrightarrow A-BS is approximated by

$$E_{b,u} \approx \log_2 \left(\frac{\sigma_{b,u}^2}{(\sigma_{a,u}^2)^{1 - \frac{N_r}{N}} (\sigma_w^2)^{\frac{N_r}{N}}} \right). \quad (18)$$

Consequently, to minimize eavesdropped information by the hacker, it should satisfy that $N_r \rightarrow N$, where it points out that the number of OFDM symbols within one slot should be, at maximum, the required time for hacking the precoders given by the FA.

For the sake of comparison, the ASR for the AN [10] is also given. Following (15), the ASR can be expressed as

$$E_{b,u}^a = \frac{N_r}{N} (C_{b,u} - C_{a,u}) + \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) (C_{b,u} - C_{a,\eta}), \quad (19)$$

$$C_{a,u} = \alpha \frac{\sigma_{b,u}^2}{\sigma_w^2 + (1 - \alpha)}, \quad C_{a,\eta} = \alpha \frac{\sigma_{a,u}^2}{\sigma_w^2}, \quad (20)$$

where α denotes the percentage of power devoted to the transmission of the data symbols and $1 - \alpha$ corresponds to the power allocated to the transmission of the artificial noise.

C. Fake Data Injection: Probability of Fake Symbol Detection

The probability of fake data detection is obtained for the false data injection stage: it measures the probability of the A-BS tricking the legitimate receiver into demodulating the fake data. Hence, this receiver is retrieving both the original and false symbols sent by the legitimate transmitter and Eve, respectively. Depending on the signal strength of both signals and the noise, the receiver may wrongly decode the fake data injected by A-BS instead of the original one.

In consequence, the probability of fake symbol detection in the proposed system can be defined as

$$P_r = \frac{N_r}{N} P_1 + \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) P_2, \quad (21)$$

where P_1 and P_2 are the probabilities of decoding the fake message sent by the A-BS before and after finding out the employed combiners, respectively.

It is clear that before finding out the combiner, the legitimate receiver will not be able to decode the false message ($P_1 = 0$). Hence, (21) can be simplified as

$$P_r = \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) P_2. \quad (22)$$

To demodulate the injected signal by A-BS at any legitimate receiver, its power should be higher than the power threshold, and hence the resilience probability can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} P_2 &= Pr\left(|h_{a,u,n}|^2 > \sigma_{b,u}^2 + \sigma_w^2\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma_{b,u}^2 + \sigma_w^2}{\sigma_{a,u}^2}\right), \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Finally, substituting (23) in (22), the probability of detecting fake symbols can be rewritten as

$$P_r = \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right) \exp\left(-\frac{\sigma_{b,u}^2 + \sigma_w^2}{\sigma_{a,u}^2}\right). \quad (24)$$

Again, it is showing that the length of the slot should be, at maximum, the time required to hack the combiner to prevent fake data injection and ensure a secure communication system.

IV. NUMERICAL RESULTS

This section presents the numerical outcomes and defines the required parameters to perform them. When statistical significance is required, 500 Monte Carlo iterations are performed over a vector of 10^4 transmitted 4QAM symbols. We consider a subcarrier spacing of 15 kHz for $K = 600$ subcarriers and a noise figure of 13 dB. In addition to the continuous phase variation at the antenna ($\theta_{b,n}$ and $\theta_{u,n}$), a randomly selected phase from a codebook implies the unrealistic case that the drop can be quickly moved to any position in the tube. The channel model is selected to be compliant with the 3GPP Urban Micro scenario [17].

Figure 4 shows the SER performance at the eavesdropper for different phase changes of the FA. Two different schemes are used to quantify the effect of the phase rotation on the communication level, denoted by the subindexes c and f . They account for the two different ways of varying the phase shift $\theta_{b,u}$. The former assumes a continuous variation in steps of θ_c , whereas the latter varies randomly between the set of possible phase shifts. It was implemented to test whether phase values have a major impact on the performance of the proposed system. Regardless of the phase change, $\theta = 0$ corresponds to the static case, which is used as the reference one.

Fig. 4. Symbol Error Rate at the eavesdropper for different θ_c , θ_f and maximum phase change.

Fig. 5. ASR comparison. Proposed methodology and Artificial Noise with different power values.

Firstly, it can be seen that the two considered strategies have a similar performance, which motivates the use of a linear, continuous topology for the FA, as its design is much simpler when compared to random port positioning. Nevertheless, selected values for the physical dimensions of the FA are very relevant. Hence, maximum phase variations of the design are limited accordingly. This parameter is set to 40° unless specified otherwise. Generally, for maximum phase shifts greater than symbol phase spacing, 45° in the case of 4QAM, the SER is maximum, which means that no information can be extracted by the eavesdropper. Note that this is also dependent on the index of the employed modulation. Elaboration on different modulation schemes will be addressed in future work, as the mentioned phase shift would surely have an impact on the performance of the device.

In Fig. 5, the comparison in terms of ASR between the proposed technique and the AN [10] is given. Let us define η_s as

$$\eta_s = \left(1 - \frac{N_r}{N}\right), \quad (25)$$

which indicates how many OFDM symbols the hacker can eavesdrop in a slot. The worst-case scenario is $\eta_s = 1$, which implies that it is able to eavesdrop the full slot. The plot shows that our proposed scheme for any η_s (dark blue) is always outperforming the existing solution based on AN given in (19) for transmission powers till 13 dBm. For the case of higher transmission powers, the proposed precoding for

Fig. 6. Probability of fake data injection.

$\eta > 0.1$ is still better as compared to AN. The rationale is that the suggested technique is convenient since, unlike AN, it is able to utilize all of the energy because the precoding and combining matrices do not deduct the power of the data symbols.

The probability of fake data injection is plotted in figure 6 for different values of η_s . The proposed methodology also prevents the injection of malicious data where the AN is not able to. Variations in antenna topology and structure would be captured by the plotted probability, therefore, best and worst cases can be obtained. It confirms that proving a more robust system by constantly changing the precoder (and the configuration of the liquid antenna) is capable of providing greater protection.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This work demonstrates the promising potential of FA based on liquid alloys to enhance the security of communication systems, which is crucial in its evolution to 6G and beyond. Leveraging their inherent reconfigurability, we introduced a novel precoding technique that integrates the physical configuration of the liquid antenna to strengthen data secrecy. Theoretical analysis and numerical simulations confirm that the proposed method effectively protects against eavesdropping. Moreover, the system exhibits resilience to external fake data injection, as such interference is interpreted as incorrect symbols rather than compromising the actual information.

Overall, this work highlights practical use cases for FA in PLS, paving the way for their integration into next-generation communication devices.

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